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#                                                                 #  
# Site response analysis of a soil deposit with a                #  
# parabolically varying shear wave velocity profile on an      #  
# elastic half-space. The finite rigidity of the                #  
# underlying medium is considered through the use of a          #  
# viscous damper at the base of the soil column.                #  
#                                                                 #  
#   Created by:  Chris McGann                                     #  
#                HyungSuk Shin                                  #  
#                Pedro Arduino                                   #  
#                Peter Mackenzie-Helnwein                       #  
#                --University of Washington--                    #  
#                                                                 #  
# ---> Basic units are kN and m   (unless specified)           #  
#                                                                 #  
#####
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Modified by AF Kowal, 2020 - 2021, University of Otago

wipe

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-----  
# 1. DEFINE ANALYSIS PARAMETERS  
#-----  
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#---SOIL GEOMETRY

number of soil layers

set numLayers 6

layer thicknesses (m)

#set layerThick(6) 1.0

#set layerThick(5) 1.0

#set layerThick(4) 1.0

#set layerThick(3) 1.0

#set layerThick(2) 1.0

#set layerThick(1) 1.0

layer thicknesses (m)

set layerThick(6) 5.0

set layerThick(5) 10.0

set layerThick(4) 10.0

set layerThick(3) 25.0

set layerThick(2) 50.0

set layerThick(1) 100.0

#---MATERIAL PROPERTIES

soil mass density (Mg/m³)

set rho(6) 1.6

set rho(5) 2.0

set rho(4) 2.2

set rho(3) 2.3

set rho(2) 2.575

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set rho(1)    2.6

# soil shear wave velocity for each layer (m/s)
set Vs(6)    135
set Vs(5)    180
set Vs(4)    280
set Vs(3)    900
set Vs(2)    2300
set Vs(1)    2800

# soil shear modulus for each layer (kPa)
for {set k 1} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
    set G($k)    [expr $rho($k)*$Vs($k)*$Vs($k)]
}

# poisson's ratio of soil
set nu        0.25

# soil elastic modulus for each layer (kPa)
for {set k 1} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
    set E($k)    [expr 2*$G($k)*(1+$nu)]
}

# soil bulk modulus for each layer (kPa)
for {set k 1} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
    set bulk($k) [expr $E($k)/(3*(1-2*$nu))]
}

# soil cohesion (kPa)
set cohesion(6)    30
set cohesion(5)    80
set cohesion(4)    160
set cohesion(3)    300
set cohesion(2)    600
set cohesion(1)    1200

# peak shear strain
set gammaPeak    0.1

# soil friction angle
set phi          0

# reference pressure
set refPress     80

# pressure dependency coefficient
set pressCoeff   0

# bedrock shear wave velocity (m/s)
set rockVS       2800.0
# bedrock mass density (Mg/m^3)
set rockDen      2.6

#---GROUND MOTION PARAMETERS

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# time step in ground motion record
set motiondT      0.005
# number of steps in ground motion record
#set motionSteps  14000
set motionSteps   16000

#---WAVELENGTH PARAMETERS
# highest frequency desired to be well resolved (Hz)
set fMax          100.0
# shear wave velocity desired to be well resolved
set vsMin         $Vs(6)
# wavelength of highest resolved frequency
set wave          [expr $vsMin/$fMax]
# number of elements per one wavelength
set nEle          8

#---RAYLEIGH DAMPING PARAMETERS
set pi            3.141592654
# damping ratio
set damp          0.1
# lower frequency
set omega1        [expr 2*$pi*0.2]
# upper frequency
set omega2        [expr 2*$pi*20]
# damping coefficients
set a0            [expr 2*$damp*$omega1*$omega2/($omega1 + $omega2)]
set a1            [expr 2*$damp/($omega1 + $omega2)]
puts "damping coefficients: a_0 = $a0; a_1 = $a1"

#---ANALYSIS PARAMETERS
# Newmark parameters
set gamma         0.5
set beta          0.25

#-----
# 2. DEFINE MESH GEOMETRY
#-----

# trial vertical element size
set hTrial        [expr $wave/$nEle]

set numTotalEle  0
# loop over layers to determine appropriate element size
for {set k 1} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {

    # trial number of elements
    set nTrial     [expr $layerThick($k)/$hTrial]

    # round up if not an integer number of elements
    if { $nTrial > [expr floor($layerThick($k)/$hTrial)] } {
        set numEleY($k) [expr int(floor($layerThick($k)/$hTrial)
+1)]
    }
}

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    } else {
        set numEleY($k) [expr int($nTrial)]
    }
    puts "number of vertical elements in layer $k: $numEleY($k)"

# counter for total number of elements
set numTotalEle [expr $numTotalEle + $numEleY($k)]

# final vertical size of elements (m)
set sizeEleY($k) [expr {$layerThick($k)/$numEleY($k)}]
puts "vertical size of elements in layer $k: $sizeEleY($k)"
}
puts "total number of vertical elements: $numTotalEle"

# define horizontal size of elements as smallest vertical element
size (m)
set sizeEleX $sizeEleY(1)
for {set k 2} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
    if { $sizeEleY($k) < $sizeEleY([expr $k-1]) } {
        set sizeEleX $sizeEleY($k)
    }
}
puts "horizontal size of elements: $sizeEleX"

# number of nodes in vertical direction in each layer
set numTotalNode 0
for {set k 1} {$k < $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
    set numNodeY($k) [expr 2*$numEleY($k)]
    puts "number of nodes in layer $k: $numNodeY($k)"
    set numTotalNode [expr $numTotalNode + $numNodeY($k)]
}
set numNodeY($numLayers) [expr 2*($numEleY($numLayers)+1)]
puts "number of nodes in layer $numLayers: $numNodeY($numLayers)"
set numTotalNode [expr $numTotalNode + $numNodeY($numLayers)]
puts "total number of nodes: $numTotalNode"

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#-----
# 3. DEFINE NODES FOR SOIL ELEMENTS
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#-----

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# soil nodes are created in 2 dimensions, with 3 dof (2
translational, 1 porePressure)
model BasicBuilder -ndm 2 -ndf 2

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set yCoord 0.0
set count 0
# loop over layers
for {set k 1} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
    # loop over nodes
    for {set j 1} {$j <= $numNodeY($k)} {incr j 2} {
        node [expr $j+$count] 0.0 $yCoord
        node [expr $j+$count+1] $sizeEleX $yCoord
    }
}

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        set yCoord [expr {$yCoord + $sizeEleY($k)}]
    }
    set count [expr $count+$numNodeY($k)]
}
puts "Finished creating all soil nodes..."

#-----
#-----
# 4. DEFINE BOUNDARY CONDITIONS AND EQUAL DOF
#-----
#-----

# define equal DOF for simple shear deformation of soil elements
for {set k 3} {$k <= $numTotalNode} {incr k 2} {
    equalDOF $k [expr $k+1] 1 2
}

puts "Finished creating all boundary conditions and equalDOF..."

#-----
#-----
# 5. DEFINE SOIL MATERIALS
#-----
#-----

# loop over layers to define materials
for {set k 1} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
    nDMaterial PressureIndependMultiYield $k 2 $rho($k) $G($k) $bulk($k)
    $cohesion($k) $gammaPeak \
                                $phi $refPress
    $pressCoeff 20
}

puts "Finished creating all soil materials..."

#-----
#-----
# 6. DEFINE SOIL ELEMENTS
#-----
#-----

set wgtX 0.0

set wgtY(1) [expr -9.81*$rho(1)]
set wgtY(2) [expr -9.81*$rho(2)]
set wgtY(3) [expr -9.81*$rho(3)]
set wgtY(4) [expr -9.81*$rho(4)]
set wgtY(5) [expr -9.81*$rho(5)]
set wgtY(6) [expr -9.81*$rho(6)]

puts "Defining wgtX and wgtY completed"

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```

set count 0
# loop over layers
for {set k 1} {$k <= $numLayers} {incr k 1} {
  # loop over elements
  for {set j 1} {$j <= $numEleY($k)} {incr j 1} {

    set nI [expr 2*($j+$count) - 1]
    set nJ [expr $nI + 1]
    set nK [expr $nI + 3]
    set nL [expr $nI + 2]

    element quad [expr $j+$count] $nI $nJ $nK $nL 1.0
    "PlaneStrain" $k 0.0 0.0 $wgtX $wgtY($k)

  }
  set count [expr $count + $numEleY($k)]
}

puts "Finished creating all soil elements..."

#-----
# 7. CREATE RECORDERS
#-----

# reset time and analysis
setTime 0.0
wipeAnalysis

# recorder time step
set recdT [expr 1.0*$motiondT]

# record nodal displacements, velocities, and accelerations at each
time step
recorder Node -file acceleration_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-nodeRange 1 $numTotalNode -dof 1 2 acc
recorder Node -file displacement_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-nodeRange 1 $numTotalNode -dof 1 2 disp
recorder Node -file velocity_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-nodeRange 1 $numTotalNode -dof 1 2 vel

# record stress and strain at each gauss point in the soil elements
#recorder Element -file stress1_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 1 stress
#recorder Element -file stress2_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 2 stress
#recorder Element -file stress3_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 3 stress
#recorder Element -file stress4_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 4 stress
#recorder Element -file stress5_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 3 stress

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```
#recorder Element -file stress6_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 4 stress
```

```
#recorder Element -file strain1_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 1 strain
```

```
#recorder Element -file strain2_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 2 strain
```

```
#recorder Element -file strain3_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 3 strain
```

```
#recorder Element -file strain4_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 4 strain
```

```
#recorder Element -file strain5_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 3 strain
```

```
#recorder Element -file strain6_StBeach.out -time -dT $motionDT
-eleRange 1 $numTotalEle material 4 strain
```

```
puts "Finished creating all recorders..."
```

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#-----
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```
# 8. DYNAMIC ANALYSIS
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#-----
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```
# define constant factor for applied velocity
set cFactor [expr $sizeEleX*$rockDen*$rockVS]
```

```
# define velocity time history file
# input velocity series obtained from ground motion simulations,
# deconvolved to the bed rock
set velocityFile
Electronic_Supplementary_Document_E_velocityHistory.out
```

```
# timeseries object for force history
set mSeries "Path -dt $motionDT -filePath $velocityFile -factor
$cFactor"
```

```
# loading object
pattern Plain 10 $mSeries {
    load 1 1.0 0.0
}
puts "Dynamic loading created..."
```

```
# analysis objects
constraints Transformation
test NormDispIncr 1e-4 35 1
#test NormDispIncr 1e-3 15 1
algorithm Newton
numberer RCM
system ProfileSPD
integrator Newmark $gamma $beta
rayleigh $a0 $a1 0.0 0.0
analysis Transient
```

```
#analyze      $nSteps $dT
analyze      $motionSteps $motiondT

puts "Finished with dynamic analysis..."

wipe
```